

GHAZNAVID DYNASTY

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Introduction: The Ghaznavid dynasty was a Persianate Muslim dynasty that ruled over a substantial empire in parts of present-day Iran, Afghanistan, and Pakistan from the late 10th century to the early 12th century. The founder of the Ghaznavid dynasty was AlpTigin, who established the dynasty's rule in the region of Ghazna (modern-day Ghazni, Afghanistan). The Ghaznavid state was founded by Sabuktegin. The name of the state is derived from the city of Ghazna, the capital of the kingdom. In exchange for their services, the Turkic ghulams received the right from the somanis to govern the various provinces of Khurosan and Afghanistan (Ghazna, Kabul, etc. When Sabuktegin was made Viceroy and army official of the province of Ghazna (977), he came to govern these estates independently. Sabuktegin's political prestige is further enhanced in the process of tormenting the Turkish warlords Abu Ali Simjuri (son of Abulhasan Simjuri) and Foyiq troops, where the United army led by the somonian Emir Noah ibn Mansur and noib Sabuktegin rebelled in 2 battles in Khorasan in 994-995. The heightened period of the Ghaznavid state dates back to the years of the reign of Emir Sabuktegin, especially Sultan Mahmud Ghaznavid. The borders of the Ghaznavid State, which by the beginning of the 11th century had become one of the most powerful states of the Muslim East, extended to the cities of Ray and Isfahan in the West, the Caspian Sea and the Khorezm and Aral Sea in the northwest, while in the East it included a large part of northern India and reached After the demise of the Ghaznavid somonian dynasty, Mahmud annexed their entire territory in Khurosan, later the Khwarezmian state (1017), as part of his dynasty. However, their interests clashed with the karakhanids as the Ghaznavids began a struggle to take over the territory of Northern Tokharistan (present-day Surkhandarya region and southern Tajikistan) in addition to Southern Tokharistan (present-day northern Afghanistan). As a result of bitter struggles, Chaganiyon and Termez were subjugated to the Ghaznavids. The border between the Ghaznavids and the karakhanid state has been hailed as Amudarya. In 1024-1025, Mahmud accompanied Amudarya near Ghaznavi Termez, attacking Sugd through the iron gate (Iron sack) and going as far as Samarkand. As a result of these military campaigns, the provinces as far as Omul (Chorjöy) left karakhanid rule and came under ghaznavite influence. During this period, the Ghaznavid state had become a major Muslim state in the East.

However, during the reign of Mahmud Ghaznavi's son and Crown Prince Mas'ud Ghaznavi (1030-1041), the Ghaznavi state gradually began to decline, seizing the territories under its control one by one.

From the middle of the 11th century, the main rival of the Ghaznavids was the Seljuqs. Khwarezm was the 1st to secede from the Ghaznavid state. Upon the death of Iltutmish, the Viceroy of Ghaznavism (1032), his son Horun rebelled against the Ghaznavians (1034). He established friendly relations with the Seljuqs and Karakhanids, declaring Khwarezm to be independent of the Ghazni. At this time, another fierce struggle began between the Karakhanids and the Ghaznavids for the possession of Chaganyan, Khuttalon, Termiz.

After Mas'ud Ghaznavid's army was relieved of the Seljuqs at the Battle of Dandanakon near Marv (May 1040), the Ghaznavis withdrew from Khurasan altogether. The defeated Sultan Mas'ud fled to Ghaznavid Ghazna and was later killed by the conspirators (1041). The throne was ascended by Mas'ud's younger brother Muhammad. But Mas'ud's son Mavdud (1041-1048) overcame his uncle Muhammad's army, killed him, and ascended the throne. Sultan Mavdud's efforts to reclaim the provinces of the upper Amudarya ended inconclusively. The actions of Sultan Farrukhzad (1053-1059) were effective for some time, and he defeated the Seljuq Army in two consecutive battles. But later Alp Arslan managed to defeat the Ghazni. In accordance with the agreement concluded between the two (1059), the Ghaznavids lost any rights to Movarounnahr and Tokharistan. Their territory was limited to the Ghazna region and parts of northern India (Punjab, etc). The area also gradually shrank from the early 12th century. In the 60s of the 12th century, the Ghurid state completely squeezed the Ghaznavids into northern India, the capital was moved from Ghazna to Lohur (1161). When the army of Ghurid's ruler Ghiyosiddin Muhammad invaded Lahore, the Ghaznavite state was completely liquidated (1186).

State management. In the Ghaznavid state, the management system attracts attention with its complexity. At the heart of the management system stood the dargah and devons (ministries). The dargah included services and deeds related to the activities of the supreme ruler. Of particular note is the role of the hajiblik service under the Ghaznavids. In the activities of the dargah, the role of career and services such as sipohdor (courtier), davotdor (keeper of the documents of the supreme ruler), pardador (mahram; executor of khufian Affairs), dignitary (middle official at court), treasurer, Joma Khana and cleaner was great. The devons were executive offices, with 5 Devonian names appearing in contemporary sources. They are the minister's office (the Office of the prime

minister); the Office of military affairs; the Office of embassy and other official events; the Office of finance; the post office. The head of the province was called governor and appointed by the supreme ruler. Management in the regions was carried out by the Emir.

The head of the city was called the chairman. Officials such as shih-na, kutwol (commandant of the Fort), Sahib Devan (administrative steward) were also active on a citywide scale. The Ghaznavid state had a powerful military army. The supreme command was at the disposal of the ruler. The commander – in-chief, sipohsolor, was considered the most trusted representative of the dynasty or a member of that household. Mahmud Ghaznawi had qualified his younger brother Muhammad Yusuf for the position of sipohsolor. The senior military army-chiefs were said to be salor, while the middle ranks were said to be sarhang. The military had its own post office and security services. The Ghaznavids also included warships (River and Navy).

Culture. In the Ghaznavid state, science and culture developed, in particular, literature. In addition to his native Turkic, Mahmud Ghaznavid was fluent in Persian, Arabic, even Pahlavi, and he himself had finished his poems. More than 400 scholars, poets and artists gathered at his court and engaged in active work. Abu Rayhan Beruniy, as well as poets like Farrukhiy, Unsuriy, Manuchehriy, Nasir Khusrav, Utbi, Gardizi, Bayhaqi were among them and lived in Ghazna. Beruniy dedicated his "Law Mas'udi" and Bayhaqi dedicated his "Ta'rihi Mas'udi" to Mas'ud Ghaznavi. Firdavsi presented his famous epic "The Dawn" to Mahmud Ghaznavi. However, the Great Physician Abu Ali ibn Sino refused to go to Ghazna-the Sultan's court. The process of Islamization and Turkification of northern India dates back precisely to the Ghaznavite period.

Conclusion: The Ghaznavid state also placed great emphasis on construction and architecture. Many madrasas, mosques, khanakas, palaces and gardens were built in Ghazna, Balkh, Nishopur, Lohur and other cities, and libraries operated. In particular, the capital city of Ghazna flourished.

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